

eLearning Didactics for Adults

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Abstract

eLearning describes the learning processes using electronic media, like internet-technologies, learning platforms or online services, making possible, to work on learning contents independently of time and place.

The OECD ¹ divided the reasons for the use of eLearning-Technologies in two categories:

??Educational affairs, which cannot be mastered without technologies.

- the dematerialisation of learning place and time (anytime, anywhere)*
- learning-access for everybody*
- internet entrance for constantly increasing educational resources and service achievements*
- inputs for job oriented learning with a research character*
- learning on demand*
- distant learning with IT tools for equal learners*

??Educational references, which could proceed much better using information technologies ²

- an optional working style of learning*
- customer-oriented and individualized learning materials*
- individual learning procedures*
- self-checking and monitoring of the own learning process*
- communication between the participants and tutors during the learning activity*
- interactive access to education servers*

The following article is concerned with the didactical and technical requirements of eLearning offered for adults. Today the internet-based learning, which is not only offered for adults, already stays far behind the given technical possibilities.

¹ OECD, eLearning, The Partnership challenge, OECD, Paris 2001

² OECD, Learning to Change: ICT in Schools, OECD, Paris, 2001

The pedagogic sees the solution of life problems as its task by appropriate learning offers. These are pointed out in a first step. After this general educational part, the article will focus on the specific situation of adult and further training ones. Social and biographic problems are represented.

These cause a tuned didactic to fit the needs for an adult learner. The steadily increasing gap between users and nonusers cannot be closed by the huge dimension of mass media and the internet.

The substantial conceptions and components of an eLearning-Space are discussed in the last section. The focus is on the different needs of teachers and instructors as well as on those for the individual learner. Different virtual learning areas are presented and their borders and possibilities are discussed.
